

Quantum Average Momentum Compared with Classical Statistical Pressure

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Classical statistical pressure is calculated by averaging $2pv$ where $2p$ is the momentum change related to an impulse hit $\int F dt$ (i.e. the particle bounces back) and v is related to flux which in turn is linked to time or the number of particles with momentum p in a certain volume which strike a surface in a given time interval. The time units in the flux term v cancel dt time units in the impulse.

We have argued in previous notes that within a quantum wavelength \hbar/p (from $\exp(ipx)$) there is no internal time (although there is an external one linked with $x=p/m t$). The two dimensions of $\exp(ipx)$ account for the direction of motion and so time is not needed internally. [Given that $\exp(ipx)$ contains p which in turn is linked to v , there is an external time in the picture, but not an internal one, we argue.] The quantum bound state problem is statistical, but there is only one particle and no time. Thus instead of considering an average of $p v$, one may consider an average of the impulse i.e. average momentum given by $-2i dW/dx / W$ where W is the wavefunction. (A bound state wavefunction is real so the i factor indicates that the momentum is not associated with the entire system translating i.e. it is a bound state.)

Impulse, however, is $\int F dt$ in classical physics, so an average $2p$ treated as an average impulse contains some kind of average time term. We argue that this seems to be \hbar/E in a quantum system. In order for the quantum system to mimic a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas, we argue that the force $-dV/dx$ at x should match $\hbar/E * \text{average impulse at } x$. There is no spatial density in $W(x)$ ($W^*(x)W(x)$ is spatial density) so one does not need to consider a little box, as in the classical statistical mechanical case. Interestingly, there is a quantum case in which this situation arises, namely the oscillator ground state.

Classical Statistical Pressure and Pressure Balance

The idea of classical pressure is based on the notion of impulse. A particle with momentum p imparts an impulse $\int F dt$ of $2p$ on a surface if it bounces back with the same p magnitude value. Thus if one has a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas, a volume contains particles with different momenta in a weighted manner given by $f(p) = C \exp(-pp/2mT)$. The particles with different momenta, however, travel with different speeds so the incoming flux is proportional to the velocity v . Thus a high speed particle may have a small $f(p)$, but a high flux. As a result, pressure (based on impulse hits) is given by (see (1)):

$$\text{Pressure} = \text{constant} \int C dp \exp(-pp/ (2mT)) 2p v \quad ((1)) \text{ one dimension}$$

$$\text{Overall the pressure in an ideal gas is given by: } PV = nRT \text{ or } P=RT n/V = RT \text{ density}(x) \quad ((2))$$

There are two points we wish to make. First, density is associated with a volume (or length in 1D). Secondly, the notion of impulse is central. Impulse, however, implies $\int F dt$ so there is a time present, but flux represents particles per time and so the "time" values cancel so to

speak, but the notion of time exists and is key, otherwise there would be no notion of flux proportional to v .

Given that density appears in ((2)), this seems to imply one must consider a little volume in calculations, meaning one considers pressure $P(x)$ and $P(x+dx)$ in one dimension. This should balance $-dV/dx * \text{density}(x)$ where $-dV/dx = \text{force}$. This standard result is in keeping with the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution:

$$P(x,T) = C1 \exp(-pp/2mT) \exp(-V(x)/T) \quad ((3))$$

where density is proportional to $\exp(-V(x)/T)$.

The question we ask is: How should the above considerations carry over into quantum mechanics, for example into a quantum bound state?

Quantum Mechanics and Impulse

In the above section a spatial density in the presence of a potential $V(x)$ was assumed, in fact this density is given by ((3)). Quantum mechanics also has a spatial density (although not equal to ((3)) in general). The density is given by:

$$\text{density}(x) = W^*(x)W(x) \quad ((4a)) \quad \text{where } W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx) \quad ((4b))$$

One does not, however, need to think in terms of the density, $W(x)$ suffices for the arguments here.

In a quantum bound state the notion of $V(x)$ and $-dV/dx$ exist and p is momentum, thus the idea of an impulse hit of $2p$ associated with $\text{Integral } Fdt$ should also apply. [Experimentally photons have been found to impart impulses on thin foils.] One difference is that there is only one particle in a quantum single particle scenario, but we argue that there is a more important difference namely regarding time.

In the classical situation, the notion of time is critical because otherwise there would be no notion of flux proportional to v . As noted, v goes as $1/\text{time}$ and this "cancels in terms of units" the time which appears in $\text{Integral } F dt$. In the quantum bound picture, we argue there is only an instantaneous notion of time at the root-mean-square level. In particular:

$$\text{Kinetic energy} = -1/2m \ d/dx \ dW/dx / W = \text{prms}(x) \ \text{prms}(x) / 2m \quad ((5))$$

$\text{prms}(x)$ is associated with an instantaneous time, but $W(x)$ is not. Furthermore, if we consider the constituents of $W(x)$, namely $\exp(ipx)$, we argue that time is absent from these, although on average there is an external time. We suggest that given the presence of a constant p , $x=p/m t$, but that this only holds on average. $\exp(ipx)$ describes two probability distributions which together define the direction of motion so time has been removed. Each represents a probability distribution $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ and so one cannot follow the particle in time. Thus the notion of a flux proportional to v does not exist, although $2p$ is still related to an impulse hit.

As a result, we suggest that in a quantum bound state, one does not take an average of $p v$ to find an expression of pressure with no time units, but rather an average of $2p$ which yields an average of $\text{Integral } F dt$ which has a time unit. Thus:

$$\text{Average impulse} = -2i dW/dx / W = \text{Sum over } p \ a(p) p \exp(ipx) / \{ \text{Sum over } p \ a(p) \exp(ipx) \} \quad ((6))$$

(The “i” may be removed as it shows that the overall bound system is not translating.)

If average impulse is to be linked to force, one needs to remove the time embedded in $\text{Integral } F dt$. How may this be done? We suggest that in the bound system, there is an internal time, namely:

$$\text{Internal time interval} = \hbar / E_n \quad \text{where } E_n \text{ is the bound state energy} \quad ((7))$$

$$\text{Thus we argue that a statistical force} = E^2 |(-idW/dx / W)| \text{ constant} \quad ((8))$$

We use $||$ to remove the “i” because we don’t want a complex result. W is guaranteed to be real for a bound state.

In a quantum bound state there is also a physical force given by $-dV/dx$. Like in the classical statistical mechanical scenario, one may suggest a balance. In the classical statistical mechanical scenario, however, one deals with a spatial density and so the idea of a little box with pressure at x and $x+dx$ is considered. $W(x)$ in ((8)) is not a spatial density (although $W^*(x)W(x)$ is), so one does not need to consider a little box. One may try to balance $-dV/dx$ at x directly with the average impulse at x i.e.

$$-dV/dx = E^2 |(-idW/dx / W)| \text{ constant} \quad ((9))$$

This begs the question: Is ((9)) ever satisfied in a quantum system?

It is in the case of the ground state oscillator. In that case: $-dV/dx = -kx$, $E = \sqrt{k/m} \cdot 0.5$ and $W(x) = C \exp(-.5\sqrt{k/m}xx)$. Thus ((9)) becomes:

$$-kx = xk \text{ constant} \quad \text{so the constant} = 1 \text{ if } \hbar=1.$$

Conclusion

In conclusion, we consider the idea of balancing $\text{Pressure}(x) = \text{density}(x) RT$ at the two walls of a little box i.e. at x and $x+dx$ with $-dV/dx$ density(x) inside the box. We argue this involves the notion of a little box and the notion of time because flux proportional to v considers how many particles hit the wall per second and this cancels (in terms of units) time in $\text{Integral } Fdt$ which brings in the notion of force through an impulse.

In the quantum mechanical case, we argue that impulse still exists i.e. $\int F dt = 2p$, but that notion of internal time does not. $\exp(ipx)$ is not associated with an internal time, although there is an external one such that $x = p/m t$. $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ are spatial distributions which together indicate the direction of motion and remove time. If $x = p/m t$ within a wavelength, one would not have a probability of $\cos(px)$. Thus for a quantum wavefunction $W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$ there is no time so no flux v term and no "little box" because $W(x)$ is not spatial density. There is, however, still the notion of $2p$ i.e. impulse. We consider the average momentum (removing the i because the system does not translate i.e. it is bound and in one place) i.e. $2\langle p \rangle = 2 \int -i dW/dx / W$. This should be the average impulse which still contains a time unit. We multiply by E/\hbar ($\hbar=1$) which is $1/\text{time}$ i.e. an internal time in the system. Thus average impulse at x is $E^2 |dW/dx / W|$ constant. We try to equate this with $-dV/dx$ in order to recreate the classical scenario. The question is: Does such a balance ever exist in a quantum bound system. We argue it appears in the quantum oscillator ground state with constant=1.

References

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<https://www.toppr.com/ask/question/using-the-maxwell-distribution-function-determine-the-pressure-exerted-by-gas-on-a-wall-if/>